

EFFECT OF LOCAL COUPLING UPON LINEAR AND NONLINEAR

BEHAVIOR OF FABRIC COMPOSITES

Takashi Ishikawa*, Masamichi Matsushima** and Yoichi Hayashi*

1st Airframe Division
National Aerospace Laboratory
1880, Jindaiji-machi, Chofu-shi, Tokyo 182, JAPAN

Abstract

The most important point for understanding macroscopic mechanical behavior of fabric composites is their local coupling effect. Even in the simplest bound theory which was developed by one of the authors (TI), the coupling term plays a key role for a theoretical description. This paper demonstrates first a clear dependency of the in-plane linear elastic modulus of plain weave fabric composites upon the number of plies. Such dependency is caused by the difference in the extent of restriction of the out-of-plane deformation due to the local coupling effect.

Secondly, this paper presents a nonlinear analysis of macroscopic behavior of plain and 8-H satin composites. Geometrical and material nonlinearities are taken into account. A description of the out-of-plane deformation by the coupling term in the deformed shape is essential in considering the geometrical nonlinearity. Four kinds of nonlinear material behavior are taken into account for carbon/epoxy systems: softening type of behavior in the pure matrix region, the nonlinear shear behavior related to the crimped yarns, local "knee" effect in the transverse yarns to loads, and a hardening nonlinearity in the pure UD parts under longitudinal tensile loads. The last behavior is recently identified and the new constitutive relations are introduced for the present theoretical approach.

Some experiments are conducted for the validation of the theory. Theoretical predictions coincide well with experimental results in general. Through such a comparison, the importance of the local coupling effect in the mechanics of fabric composites is clearly understood.

*: Senior Researcher, and **: Researcher

Introduction

Practical applications of 2-dimensional fabric composites have been increasing in the area of advanced composite technology. Aircraft composite structures such as Learfan 2100 (1) can be designated as a good example. Along with wide-spreading employments of the fabric reinforcements, their mechanics have also been unveiled in the series of the publications by one of the authors (II), Refs. (2),(3),(4) and (5). The most important point in this mechanics is the local coupling effect between in- and out-of-plane deformation due to the interlacing structure of fabrics. Macroscopic behavior of fabric composites is strongly governed by this effect. The upper and lower bounds of the elastic stiffness derived from the simplest theory (2) are widely open because of a consideration of the coupling term.

The results of an effort for a tighter bounding is stated at the first part of this paper mainly for the plain weave composites. Two extreme cases are considered where the out-of-plane deformation is completely allowed and it is fully prohibited. Even so, there still remains a considerable discrepancy between the two cases, which can be regarded as the tightened bounds. Some experiments for determining the in-plane linear elastic moduli of plain and 8-H satin composites are conducted. The experimental results of plain weave carbon/epoxy systems vary between the extreme values and exhibit a clear dependency upon the number of plies. A comparison of the theory and experiments leads us to the recognition of the role of the local coupling effect in such a dependency.

The second part of this paper treats a tensile nonlinear behavior of fabric composites, which is practically significant for a tension structure in space applications. Examined materials are plain and 8-H satin weave carbon/epoxy composites, similarly to the linear part. Both geometrical and material sources of nonlinearity are included in the framework of the theory. The local coupling is again crucial in the case of thin plain weave composites because it induces some out-of-plane deformation and requires a mathematical description in the deformed state. Four different types of sources of material nonlinearity are taken into account in the formulation. The most remarkable type is a hardening behavior in longitudinal tension inherent to carbon composites. A new constitutive relation is proposed for describing this phenomenon. Stress-strain relations are experimentally obtained for concerned fabric composites and compared with the theoretical solutions.

Linear Behavior

Tightening the Bound Theory

The theoretical part for the calculation of the elastic moduli have already been published in the quoted papers, (2) - (5). A duplication, therefore, is avoided here as much as possible. The theoretical backbone is always a well-known laminate theory. We cannot skip the description of the constitutive equation, partly for nomenclature, as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_i \\ M_i \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{ij} & B_{ij} \\ B_{ij} & D_{ij} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_j^0 \\ \kappa_j \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1) \quad , \quad \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_i^0 \\ \kappa_i \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{ij}^* & b_{ij}^* \\ b_{ij}^* & d_{ij}^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N_j \\ M_j \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

We will follow the definition of $A_{ij} \dots$, $a_{ij}^* \dots$ etc., after the regular manner in Ref. (6) or Ref. (3). The simplest bound theory is directly derived as stated Refs. (2) and (3). The following straightforward cancel-

lation of the coupling term based on the mosaic model (3);

$$\bar{B}_{ij} = (1 - 2/n_g) B_{ij} \quad (3)$$

is resulting in the wide bounds. By assuming one strip of the mosaic model along the load direction, we reach the lower bound solution (3). Figure 1 depicts the lower bound indicated by LB and the coincident finite element results (3) indicated by the open circles.

If we do not allow any out-of-plane deformation, the following conditions hold:

$$\{\kappa_i\} = 0, \quad \{M_i\} \neq 0 \quad (4)$$

These conditions leads to the one-to-one inversion between A_{ij} and the bending free compliance a_{ij}^{**} , such as,

$$[a_{ij}^{**}] = [a_{ij}^*] - [b_{ik}^*] [d_{kl}^*]^{-1} [b_{lj}^*] = [A_{ij}]^{-1} \quad (5)$$

This equation means that the coupling terms do not make sense any more under the bending-free condition and that the upper bound indicated by UB in Fig. 1 is the only possible solution because it is not affected Eq. (3). The bound solutions, therefore, are naturally discrepant so long as we admit the aforementioned points.

A thread crimp is then considered in the analysis by employing the crimp model, as Refs. (3) and (4). An illustration of the model is shown in Fig. 2 where the sinusoidal shape of the crimp is postulated. The assumption that the laminate theory is valid in an infinitesimal slice with the length of dx is required for the formulation. The above extreme conditions of no curvature are also applicable to this model. Such a state may be fictitiously realised by an ideally symmetrical arrangement of the model with respect to the xy plane. First, we evaluate the local bending-free compliance by a simple inversion of the local in-plane stiffness, as:

$$[a_{ij}^{**}(x)] = [A_{ij}(x)]^{-1} \quad (6)$$

An actual calculation of $A_{ij}(x)$ can be done with the knowledge of the stiffness distribution in the thickness direction of the crimp model, like Eq. 15 in Ref. (4). By replacing this $a_{ij}^{**}(x)$ for $a_{ij}^*(x)$ in the averaging process of the compliance along the crimp model, i.e., in Eq. 7 in Ref. (3), we have:

Figure 1 - Non-dimensionalized in-plane modulus by the laminate value vs. $1/n_g$. —: bound solution, o: the finite element results for the mosaic model.

Figure 2 - One-dimensional crimp model.

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{a_{ij}^{**c}} &= (2/n_g a) \cdot \int_0^{n_g a/2} a_{ij}^{**}(x) dx \\ &= (1 - 2a_u/n_g a) \cdot a_{ij}^{**} + (2/n_g a) \cdot \int_{a_0}^{a_2} a_{ij}^{**}(x) dx \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

By inverting this 3 by 3 matrix, we obtain the in-plane stiffness under the local warping(out-of-plane deformation) constrained condition, abbreviated as L.W.C. It should be noted that the previous crimp solution in Refs.(3) and (4) is corresponding to the case where no constraint on the local warping is implicitly assumed. Hence, it is referred to as Local Warping Allowed solution. Numerical results are shown in Fig. 3 where a very flat fabric geometry of $h/a = 0.1$ is adopted for $n_g = 2, 3$ and 4 . The basic material properties of the UD carbon/epoxy systems used in Figs. 1, 3, 4 and 5 are listed in Table 1. It can be seen that the bounds are slightly narrowed by L.W.C. and L.W.A. curves although there still remains a considerable gap. Note that the L.W.A. results may be smaller than the L.B. curve if we assume a strong crimp, namely, a large h/a as in Fig.1($h/a = 0.4$).

A parallel application of the L.W.C. condition is possible to the bridging model which is appropriate for the description of the macroscopic behavior of the satin weave composites (4). Although the illustration is skipped here, some conceptual equations are written below for this condition. By assuming the load re-distribution in the surrounding regions of the crimp in satin composites (4), we obtain

$$\overline{A_{ij}^{BCD}} = \{ (\sqrt{n_g} - 1)A_{ij} + \overline{A_{ij}^c} \} / \sqrt{n_g} \quad (8)$$

where the superscript BCD signifies the averages in such regions. The inversion of Eq.(7) must be employed as $\overline{A_{ij}^c}$ for satisfying the condition. An assumption of the uniformity of the loads, or a serial arrangement in the model, leads to the following equation:

$$\overline{a_{ij}^{**s}} = \{ 2 \cdot \overline{a_{ij}^{**BCD}} + (\sqrt{n_g} - 2) \cdot a_{ij}^{**} \} / \sqrt{n_g} \quad (9)$$

where the superscript s denotes a result for the entire model and where the first term in the right-hand side is obtained by the inversion of Eq. (8). Again, the final results of the in-plane stiffness for the L.W.C. state are reached by the inversion of Eq. (9). Similarly to the crimp case, the previous results in Ref.(4) correspond to the implicit L.W.A. condition. Numerical results are indicated also in Fig.3 for $n_g \geq 4$. Note that the different h/a value ($= 0.35$) from the crimp results is used because such ratio is very common in available 8-H satin fabrics. It can be observed that

Table I - Material properties of UD thread and pure epoxy resin

Resin No.	3601	3650
E_L (GPa)	137.3	137.3
E_T (GPa)	10.79	9.807
G_{LT} (GPa)	5.394	4.805
ν_L	0.26	0.26
ν_{TT}	0.46	0.46
E_m (GPa)	4.511	4.119
ν_m	0.38	0.38

Figure 3 - Comparison of L.W.C. and L.W.A. solutions for non-dimensionalized in-plane stiffness.

both curves are closer to each other than in the case of the crimp results and that the experimental results stated later fall between the theoretical predictions.

Experiments

Some experiments for determining the in-plane elastic moduli are conducted in order to confirm the above-mentioned theory. An objective material is carbon/epoxy plain and 8-harness satin composites consistently with the analysis. Four kinds of ply numbers, 1, 4, 8 and 20, are chosen for the plain weave, whereas only 2-ply cured with the quasi-symmetric lamination (2) are tested for the 8-H satin. The plain weave consists of T-300 fibers, 3601 and 3650 (only for 4 ply) epoxy resins by Toray Co. The thread width, a , is 2mm and the ply thickness is roughly 0.2mm, so $h/a \approx 0.1$. The 8-H satin prepreg is composed of AS fibers and 410 resin by Mitsubishi Rayon Co. The thread width is 1mm and the ratio of $h/a \approx 0.35$. For both fabrics, the thread densities in the fill and warp directions are almost identical. Fiber volume fractions are measured by the burning method.

The shape of the specimen is a straight coupon of 12.5mm in width and aluminum end tabs are used. They are roughly classified into two groups, on- and off-axis specimens. Measured off-axis orientations are [+45], [15, -75], [30, -60] and [22.5, -67.5] (only for 8-H satin). Some efforts are paid for obtaining longer coupons particularly for the off-axis tests.

Strain gauges of a large extension type are mainly used for strain measurements. Because the serious strengthening effects by the gauges themselves are expected for the thinnest specimens of 1-ply plain weave composites, a pair of

Table II - Experimental results

Weave Style N (Number of Ply)	Plain				8 Harness Satin
	1	4	8	20	2
h/a	0.098	0.119	0.096	0.117	0.35
$\bar{E}_{0,90}$ (GPa)	48.3	49.8	63.1	60.7	65.2
CV^* (%)	4.75	1.69	1.30	1.46	2.07
$\bar{v}_{0,90}$	0.062 [†]	0.068	0.053	/	0.061
\bar{E}_{+45} (GPa)	18.3	13.4	19.5	/	18.0
\bar{v}_{+45}	0.70 [†]	0.76	0.75	/	0.70
$\bar{E}_{15,-75}$ (GPa)	29.2	/	46.8	/	/
$\bar{E}_{30,-60}$ (GPa)	19.6	/	22.0	/	/
$\bar{E}_{22.5,-67.5}$ (GPa)	/	/	/	/	34.7
$\bar{G}_{0,90}$ (GPa)	5.41	3.83	5.56	/	5.30
\bar{G}_{45} (GPa)	22.7	23.3	30.0	/	30.7
V_f (%)	[58.]	52.	[58.]	60.	63.

* : Coefficient of Variation.

[] : Measured by the Supplier.

+ : Measured by Gauges after Electro-optical Measurement.

electro-optical displacement detector are used as an extensometer where the gauge length is specified as 100mm. This system is used for 2-ply 8-H and 4-ply plain coupons of nearly 1mm in thickness in order to examine the extent of such effect. No clear disturbance by the interlacing region upon the gauge could be found for both plain and 8-H satin specimens. Also, precaution is taken for picking up data within the same range of strain because nonlinearity is serious in some cases. The maximum strain of 500×10^{-6} is chosen as a compromise. All experimental results are listed in Table II.

The values of the in-plane shear modulus, $G_{0,90}$ in Table II are obtained by the data of E_{45} and ν_{45} and the following well-known relation

$$G_{0,90} = E_{45} / \{2(1 + \nu_{45})\} \quad (10)$$

All results of 1-ply plain weave are based on the electro-optical measurement and a fairly large scattering in the data can be ascribed to the very delicate nature of the technique. A correction factor is determined by comparing the results by the gauges and this system for the second thinnest group, 4-ply plain and 8-H satin.

Comparison and Discussions

Experimental and theoretical results in the linear behavior are compared in Figs. 3 to 5. Figure 3 has been already shown for the in-plane stiffness as functions of the most important variable in fabrics, $1/n_g$. The cross-ply data for non-dimensionalizing are calculated directly from Table 1. Experimental results of 4-ply plain are plotted on the right edge where $1/n_g = 0.5$. The symbol ϕ signifies both the averaged value indicated by the circle and the scattering indicated by the bars. The point \times is the results of Ref. (7). A good correlation between theory and experiments can be observed for 8H satin composites. This fact suggests good predicability of the theory based upon the bridging model for satin weave composites.

The situation is different in the case of the plain weave. A constraint of the local warping is considered to be a governing factor of the gap between the L.W.C. and L.W.A. solutions in Fig. 3. Neighboring layers in a fabric laminate tend to suppress the warping of one another. Thus, a dependency of the in-plane moduli on ply quantity is suggested. This effect is demonstrated in Fig.4 where the results of four different ply numbers, N , are indicated. The upper part of Fig.4 represents A_{11} divided by that of the cross-ply and the lower part shows the results by A_{11} of the L.W.C. state. Small variations in the predictions are caused by the scattering of the measured h/a . The dependency of the in-plane moduli of the plain weave on the number of plies is obvious in Fig.4. The modulus increases from the value of 1-ply, which is slightly higher than the L.W.A. prediction, and reaches

Figure 4 - Dependency of in-plane stiffness on ply number in plain weave composites. upper: non-dimensionalized by A_{11} of laminate, lower: non-dimensionalized by L.W.C. solution for $n_g = 2$.

Figure 5 - Off-axis in-plane elastic moduli of plain weave and 8H satin.

values slightly lower than the L.W.C. predictions. Note that the leveling off in modulus occurs at 8-ply and that the value is very close to that of 8H satin as given in Table II. Hence, the discrepancy between the L.W.C. and L.W.A. solutions is quite proper in the theory where N is not explicitly treated. Such a characteristic of the plain composites is of practical importance particularly in the application for the face sheets of honeycomb sandwich structures. It should be noted that the lower modulus of 4-ply compared to the other cases can be ascribed to the lower V_f which is not included in the prediction and the resin #3650.

The in-plane off-axis moduli are discussed in Fig.5 where all quantities have a physical dimension for practical advantage. The off-axis properties is symmetrical with respect to $\phi = 45^\circ$ if it is assumed that the properties in both fill and warp directions are identical. The in-plane shear modulus at $\phi = 45^\circ$ is practically significant in wing-skin applications. The predictions exhibit some discrepancy between the L.W.C. and L.W.A. states correspondingly to the on-axis A_{11} . This fact again suggests a dependency of G_{45} on ply number, and such a suggestion is confirmed by the indicated results on the central axis in Fig.5. Off axis moduli of the plain weave in other angles also depends clearly upon their quantity of the plies. Equations 19 - 21 of Ref. (8) are adopted for the off-axis correction of the raw data measured by the strain gauges. Although a slight deviation from the theory is found, it can be concluded that the off-axis experimental results are generally in good accordance with the theory.

Nonlinear Behavior

Common Three Types of Material Nonlinearity

An analysis of macroscopic nonlinear behavior of fabric composites is basically divided into two parts: a treatment of material nonlinearity and geometrical nonlinearity. A consideration of material nonlinear behaviors is moreover classified into two sections: the former is a description of the three common nonlinearities which are included at the level of Ref. (5), and the latter is a newly identified hardening nonlinear behavior inherent to carbon composites (9). This section refers to the first part of the material nonlinearity. Because Ref. (5) treats such behavior in detail, the level of description is limited here to the minimum. It should be stated first that the confined solution to the material side is much more suitable for the L.W.C. than L.W.A. conditions. In other words, the consideration of the deformed state under the L.W.C. condition (see Fig. 6) gives almost no influence upon the final nonlinear results as explained later.

The first material behavior taken into account is the "knee" (10) phenomenon due to the extension of cracks in the transverse threads to the loads, which is similar to the case of cross-ply laminates. A probabilistic nature of this phenomenon is neglected here for simplicity and it is only assumed that the cracked area in the warp threads extends if a local strain under a tensile stress in the fill direction exceeds the specified value ϵ_2^b . Once the area is decided to be cracked, it is postulated that the following reduced stiffness should be employed:

$$Q_{ij}^W = Q_{ij}^W / 100 \quad (11)$$

: except for Q_{22}^W .

Figure 6 - Illustration of the deformed state under the local warping constrained (L.W.C.) condition: only θ is changed into θ' .

where the prime indicates the nonlinear state from here on.

The second material nonlinearity is related to the nonlinear off-axis behavior arising from the nonlinear pure shear relation analyzed in Ref. (11). An off-axis angle due to the thread crimp, θ in Fig. 2, is the cause of such a behavior. By employing the higher order compliance after the manner of Ref. (11), we can express the nonlinear compliance in the fill direction such that:

$$S_{11}^{\prime F}(\theta) = S_{11}^F(\theta) + (1 - \cos 4\theta)^2 / 64 \cdot S_{5555}^F [\sigma_1^F(\theta)]^2 \quad (12)$$

Thus, we have the nonlinear reduced stiffness:

$$[Q_{ij}^{\prime F}(\theta)] = [S_{ij}^{\prime F}(\theta)]^{-1} \quad (13)$$

The effect of S_{5555} on Poisson and in-plane shear strains is neglected in Eqs. (12, 13) and hence, $S_{12}^{\prime F}(\theta)$ and $S_{66}^{\prime F}(\theta)$ are not functions of $\sigma_1^F(\theta)$.

The third property being considered is the visco-elasto-plastic behavior in the pure matrix region also peculiar to the fabric composites. Instead of a rigorous formulation, an analogous description to the preceding shear behavior as the nonlinear elastic medium is adopted here. By defining a higher order compliance for the axial strain in the pure matrix region, S_{1111}^M , we obtain the following stress-strain relation:

$$\epsilon_i^M = S_{11}^M \sigma_i^M + S_{1111}^M (\sigma_i^M)^3 \quad ; \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (14)$$

The stiffness matrix $Q_{ij}^{\prime M}$ is reached by the inversion of Eq. (14). According to a preliminary sensitivity analysis, however, the effect of this behavior upon the final results is very limited if the content of the pure resin region is small.

An iteration procedure inevitable in most nonlinear analyses is also required here for an actual calculation. Knowing $Q_{ij}^{\prime F}(\theta)$, $Q_{ij}^{\prime M}$ and $Q_{ij}^{\prime W}$ for a given x location of the crimp model, $a_{ij}^{\prime\prime}(x)$ can be evaluated from Eq. (6). Then based upon the initial value of N_1 , and $a_{ij}^{\prime\prime}(x)$ just computed, a revised nonlinear strain $\epsilon_1^0(x)$ can be obtained. By a numerical integration technique similar to Eq. (7), we obtain an averaged $\bar{\epsilon}_1^0$ for the entire model. The difference between the initial $\bar{\epsilon}_1^0$ and revised strain is denoted by $\Delta\bar{\epsilon}_1^0$. For terminating the iteration, the following condition is imposed here:

$$|\Delta\bar{\epsilon}_1^0 / \bar{\epsilon}_1^0| \leq 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \quad (15)$$

Thus, an iteration process is required and the number of iterations needed for an acceptable revised strain increases as strain level becomes higher. Some precautions are also necessary for selecting numerical

Figure 7 - Nonlinear stress-strain relations of glass/polyimide fabric composites. —: three sources considered, ----: "knee" only,: experimental.

parameters.

Numerical stress-strain relations for glass/polyimide 8H satin composites are depicted in Fig. 7. Basic material properties are given in Table III for this system, and some crimp parameters are as follows:

$$h_t = h = 0.244 \text{ (mm)}, \quad a_u = a = 0.4 \text{ (mm)} \quad (16)$$

A solid theoretical curve for $n_g = 8$ which includes the present sources of nonlinear strains is in a good agreement with an experimental curve plotted with dots. It should be noted that the L.W.C. state is nearly realized because the specimens are very thick with 24 plies. The dashed curve for the case where only the knee behavior is included is in a poorer correlation with the experiment. Thus, we can predict a nonlinear stress-strain relationship up to the failure for thick glass fabric composites based upon the present constituent material nonlinearities and the L.W.C. condition.

Material Hardening Nonlinearity in Longitudinal Direction of Carbon Composites

For the case of carbon fabric composites, some preliminary work unveils that theoretical results based on only those 3 sources under the L.W.C. condition do not agree with experimental results to a favorable extent. The cause should be ascribed to another nonlinear behavior inherent to carbon fibers. A literature survey is conducted and a few papers which state a hardening nonlinear behavior in longitudinal tension of carbon composites are found. A dependency of the longitudinal modulus of a single carbon fiber on stress is reported first in Ref. (12). A linear empirical formula of the modulus for UD carbon composites is proposed in Ref. (13). Some other literature shows such behavior unintentionally.

In Ref. (9), it is reconfirmed that the stress-strain curves are convex downward at lower stress levels. The relationship between the experimental longitudinal moduli for carbon/epoxy coupons and stress is plotted in Fig.8 by solid circles. A rational constitutive equation is derived next from the theory of nonlinear elasticity. Basic points of the derivation are given here briefly.

Table III - Material properties of glass/polyimide UD and pure resin systems.

E_L	41.2 GPa
E_T	15.7 GPa
G_{LT}	5.59 GPa
ν_L	0.3
ν_{TT}	0.48
S_{5555}	37.0 GPa^{-3}
ϵ_2^b	0.5 %
V_f	50.0 %
<hr/>	
E_m	4.31 GPa
ν_m	0.36
S_{1111}^m	9.88 GPa^{-3}

Figure 8 - Stress dependent longitudinal moduli of unidirectional carbon/epoxy composites.

We will follow the manner of Ref.(11) for the shear nonlinearity. A favorable point to the present behavior is that loading and unloading paths are precisely identical. The application of the complementary energy function, therefore, is more convincing than to the nonlinear shear case where such good identity of paths is never found. By admitting this point, we can assume the complementary energy function W^* and have

$$e_{ij} = \partial W^* / \partial \sigma_{ij} \quad (17)$$

where e_{ij} are tensorial strains. Under the state of the longitudinal uniaxial loading of UD composites, a polynomial expansion of W^* up to 4th order yields (11),

$$W^* = \frac{1}{2} S_{11} \sigma_1^2 + \frac{1}{3} S_{111} \sigma_1^3 + \frac{1}{4} S_{1111} \sigma_1^4 \quad (18)$$

The longitudinal engineering strain ϵ_1 is then given by

$$\epsilon_1 = \partial W^* / \partial \sigma_{11} = S_{11} \sigma_1 + S_{111} \sigma_1^2 + S_{1111} \sigma_1^3 \quad (19)$$

Hence, the longitudinal elastic modulus is described by the following fractional function of the stress to the second order using higher order elastic compliance coefficients:

$$E_L = d\sigma_1 / d\epsilon_1 = 1 / (d\epsilon_1 / d\sigma_1) = 1 / (S_{11} + 2 S_{111} \sigma_1 + 3 S_{1111} \sigma_1^2) \quad (20)$$

A comparison and fitting of Eq. 20 with the experimental results in Fig. 8 provides a determination procedure of the higher order compliance coefficients. The detail of the procedure is left to Ref.(9) and only the result is given here, which is indicated by a solid line in Fig. 8:

$$E_L = 1000 / (7.634 - 2.444 \sigma_1 + 1.111 \sigma_1^2) \quad : \text{ (GPa)} \quad (21)$$

Note that this equation is obtained only by tensile tests. If we employ some other compressive data, open squares in Fig.8 adapted from Ref.6 for example, we have the following modified relation

$$E_L = 1000 / [6.689 + 0.982(\sigma_1 - 1.1)^2] \quad (22)$$

This is indicated by a dashed line in Fig. 8 and it is remarkable that both curves are quite close.

Numerical results including the present behavior (Eq. 21) are compared with the experiment for 8H satin carbon/epoxy composites in Fig. 9.

Figure 9 - Nonlinear stress-strain relations of carbon/epoxy 8H satin fabric composite. Only material nonlinearities are considered.

Table IV - Nonlinear material properties for carbon/epoxy UD composites in Fig. 9.

S_{5555}	7.29 GPa ⁻³
ϵ_2^b	0.6%
S_{1111}^m	9.88 GPa ⁻³

A chain line denotes the partial nonlinear solution where the three material properties described in the previous sub-section are considered. The nonlinear parameters of Table IV are utilized in Fig. 9. A solid line represents the fully material nonlinear solution where the present property is added to those sources. They are abbreviated as the P.M.N. and F.M.N. solutions, respectively. The experimental curve is obtained from a typical specimen referred to in the section of "Linear Behavior". As explained earlier, the local coupling effect is almost completely suppressed for these coupons. It is the reason why an initial phase of these curves are nearly identical. A correlation between the F.M.N. and experimental results is very favorable in the entire region of stress, whereas the P.M.N. solution is departing from these results at a higher stress level. The result denoted by AE represents a total count number measured by an acoustic emission device. This quantity is mainly related to the transverse crackings which are less influential in the cases of carbon than glass composites because of the relative importance of the longitudinal moduli. Thus, the nonlinear behavior of the present type is the most dominant property for a better prediction of the stress-strain relationships of carbon fabric composites under the L.W.C. state. The effect of a geometrical nonlinearity under this condition is rather small as explained next.

Geometrical Nonlinear Behavior for Thin Plain Weave Composites

Thin plain weave carbon composite is one of promising candidate materials for a tensile membrane structure in space applications. The plain weave is the only possibility for a macroscopic warping-free condition by a temperature change (2), (14) if we adopt the 1-ply membrane as the thinnest. A strong macroscopic hardening behavior has been found (15) for such a fabric plate of 1-ply carbon/epoxy. Therefore, the present problem is regarded as practically important in space technology. A consideration of the geometrical nonlinear behavior is a key factor for solving this problem. In other words, a step-by-step description of the deformed shape of the warping due to the local coupling effect is essential for the present hardening behavior. Hence, the L.W.A. condition must be imposed. Furthermore, the material properties mentioned above are maintained in the framework of the theory.

An incremental procedure is inevitable due to the nature of the problem. Let us consider an increment of the in-plane stress resultant at the i -th step, ΔN_1^i , applied on the crimp model of Fig. 2, or the specialized illustration of Fig. 10 (a). The mathematical expression should be given with respect to an immobile point during a loading process. It can be postulated that the point where $x = a/2$ and $z = 0$ is appropriate for such a condition by the consideration of symmetry and repetitiveness of the model as shown in Fig. 10 (b). By using Eq. 2, we have the following local curvature corresponding to this step:

$$\begin{aligned}
 -\Delta \partial^2 w^i / \partial x^2 &= \kappa_1^i(x) \\
 &= b_{11}^*(x)^i \Delta N_1^i
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{23}$$

Figure 10 - Schematic explanation of the deformed shape of 1-ply plane weave fabric composites.

Then, we can calculate a decrease of the local off-axis angle, $\Delta\theta^i$, such that

$$\Delta\theta^i(x) \approx \Delta(\partial w^i/\partial x) = \quad (24)$$

$$\int_0^x b_{11}^*(\xi)^i \Delta N_1^i d\xi$$

where we utilize the boundary condition that $\theta(0) = 0$ always holds by virtue of the symmetry. The change in θ naturally affects the fill stiffness $Q_{ij}^F(\theta)$, although the influence turns out to be small later on. Next, we can obtain the expression of the increment of the warping as follows:

$$\Delta w^i(x) = \int_{a/2}^x \Delta\theta^i(\xi) d\xi \quad (25)$$

where the aforementioned assumption of the immobile point is considered. An accumulated value of the warping is then calculated with the knowledge of the warping at the previous step, $w^{i-1}(x)$,

$$w^i(x) = w^{i-1}(x) + \Delta w^i(x) \quad (26)$$

This result is used as the initial value of the iteration in each i -th step. The reason why the

iterative process is required is the following. The local coupling and bending stiffness coefficients, $B_{ij}(x)$ and $D_{ij}(x)$ are affected by $w^i(x)$ because $w^i(x)$ appears the lower and upper limits of integrations along the z -axis for the actual calculation of them. As an example, a modified coupling coefficient $B_{ij}^i(x)$ at the i -th step is shown below for $0 \leq x \leq a/2$:

$$B_{ij}^i(x) = \int_{-h/2+w^i(x)}^{h_1(x)-h_t/2+w^i(x)} Q_{ij}^M z \cdot dz + \int_{h_1(x)-h_t/2+w^i(x)}^{h_1(x)+w^i(x)} Q_{ij}^F(\theta) z \cdot dz \quad (27)$$

$$+ \int_{h_1(x)+w^i(x)}^{h_2(x)+w^i(x)} Q_{ij}^W z \cdot dz + \int_{h_2(x)+w^i(x)}^{h/2+w^i(x)} Q_{ij}^M z \cdot dz$$

where Fig.2 should be referred to for the definitions of $h_1(x)$, etc. It should be noted that $A_{ij}(x)$ is not influenced by $w^i(x)$. Such modifications in $B_{ij}^i(x)$ and $D_{ij}^i(x)$ leads to those in $a_{ij}^{*i}(x)$, $b_{ij}^{*i}(x)$ and $d_{ij}^{*i}(x)$. Thus, b_{11}^* in Eq. (23) must be rewritten. This procedure consists a loop for which a convergent criterion similar to Eq. (15) should be introduced. After a converged strain is reached, next $i+1$ th step is started. It is very interesting to examine the final deformed state of Fig.10 (b). If we assume that $Q_{ij}^W \approx 0$ due to the extended transverse cracks and that Q_{ij}^M can be neglected, the following form of the warping is easily derived in order that the coupling stiffness vanishes everywhere along the fill direction:

$$w^i(x) = h_t/4 - h_1(x) = -h_t/4 \cdot \sin\{(x - a/2) \cdot \pi/a\} \quad : \text{for } a = a_u \quad (28)$$

Figure 11 - Comparison of some theoretical results with experiment in non-linear behavior of carbon(T500)/epoxy of thin plain weave.

This form implies the final straight shape of the fill. Hence, $b_{ij}^{*'}(x)$ also vanishes and no more warping occurs as explained in Eqs.(23) to (26). In other words, the deformation shape is converged into the straightened up fill thread. Such a state provides higher in-plane modulus than the initial L.W.A. solution. A simplified explanation is given below. If we assume the cylindrical bending state, in-plane compliance can be written as

$$a_{11}^{*}(x) = D_{11}(x) / [A_{11}(x) \cdot D_{11}(x) - B_{11}(x)^2] \quad (29)$$

As mentioned earlier, $B_{11}(x)$ is almost vanishing at the converged warping and it follows that $a_{11}^{*}(x)$ becomes smaller, i.e., the in-plane stiffness becomes larger. This point is a fundamental mechanism of the geometrical hardening of thin plain fabric composites.

The material nonlinear behavior is included actually in the evaluation of Eq.(27) as Q_{ij}^M , $Q_{ij}^F(\theta)$ and Q_{ij}^W . Although the detail is omitted for avoiding duplication, some comments related to the present L.W.A. situation are stated here. In the previous L.W.C. case, a strain distribution along the z-axis is uniform because of the classic laminate theory and the warping free condition. However, the strain distribution should be determined first in the present case. The following linear function to z is naturally introduced by virtue of the laminate theory:

$$\Delta \epsilon_1(z) = \Delta \epsilon_1^0 + z \cdot \Delta \kappa_1 = (a_{11}^{*} + z \cdot b_{11}^{*}) \cdot \Delta N_1 \quad (30)$$

If we cite an example of the knee behavior, it is necessary to determine the height, h_3 , where the strain reaches the critical value ϵ_2^b , as follows:

$$h_3(x) = h_2(x) - [h_2(x) - h_1(x)] \cdot [\epsilon_1^W(h_2(x)) - \epsilon_2^b] / [\epsilon_1^W(h_2(x)) - \epsilon_1^W(h_1(x))] \quad (31)$$

where $\epsilon_1^W(h)$ is a linearly distributed strain in the warp region. Then, the local in-plane stiffness is obtained as:

$$A_{ij}(x) = Q_{ij}^M [h_1(x) - h_2(x) + h - h_t/2] + Q_{ij}^F(\theta) \cdot h_t/2 \quad (32) \\ + Q_{ij}^W [h_3(x) - h_1(x)] + Q_{ij}^W [h_2(x) - h_3(x)] \quad : 0 \leq x \leq a/2$$

For more detailed points, Ref.(4) is recommended about this behavior. In the cases of Q_{ij}^M and $Q_{ij}^F(\theta)$, the variation of those stiffness is continuous along the z-direction. Therefore, they are evaluated at some discrete representative points and numerically integrated.

Experiments for obtaining the stress-strain relations are conducted for a new carbon/epoxy fabric, T500-6K/Resin X. Strip specimens of 1-ply plain weave which contain only one fill thread are made in order that the one-dimensional state in the analysis is purely realized. The same electro-optical apparatus is used as the previous tests. A typical result is indicated in Fig. 11 by a solid line with circles. It should be noted that a regular coupon specimen containing 6 or 7 threads provides a similar result to these strip pieces.

Some comments and discussions are given below for numerical results. The basic material properties of the present T-500 composite are assumed to be the same as Tables I, IV and Eq.(21) except E_L for reflecting a slight high modulus of this fiber. The value of 142. GPa is chosen as E_L and only S_{11} in Eq.(21) is changed adaptively. The abbreviation convention is maintained in Fig. 11. A pure solid line which exhibits the best agreement with the experimental curve is the solution under the L.W.A. condition and

including the four material nonlinear properties. A solid curve with crosses represents the solution where only the longitudinal hardening behavior is dropped. A dashed line corresponds to the partial geometrical nonlinear calculation where only the change in the off-axis angle in Eq.(24) is taken into account. A pair of results under the L.W.C. condition shows a considerable discrepancy from the experiment, whereas they have similar tangents to the L.W.A. results at a higher stress level. This fact is understandable according to the comments below Eq.(29). We can summarize that a initial part of the hardening characteristics of the present material is caused by the out-of-plane deformation which is captured by the geometrical nonlinear description. It is also observed that a later part is mainly governed by the longitudinal nonlinearity of carbon fibers.

A variation in the off-axis angle has just a minor influence on the stress-strain relation. In the present L.W.A. case, a consideration of this variation only leads even to an erroneous result. A geometrical nonlinear analysis of the 8H satin under the L.W.C. state illustrated in Fig.6 provides the almost identical solution to Fig.9, although a graphical presentation is skipped for avoiding too much complexity. It can be regarded as a supporting evidence for the fact that the local coupling effect is the most crucial factor in the mechanics of fabric composites.

Conclusions

- 1) The upper and lower bounds of the in-plane elastic modulus of fabric composites are improved by introducing two limiting cases concerning the local warping deformation caused by the coupling effect inherent to fabrics: completely allowed or constrained states for warping.
- 2) The experimental results of 8H satin composites are tightly bounded by these two cases with the bridging model.
- 3) There naturally remains a discrepancy in these results for plain weave composites. All on-axis measured moduli fall between the two predictions.
- 4) A dependency of in-plane moduli of plain weave composites on the number of plies is unveiled based on theoretical implication for such composites. The modulus increases with ply number and a levelling-off value is quite close to that of 8H satin. This phenomenon is caused by different restrictions of the warping by neighboring layers if existing.
- 5) Theoretical off-axis moduli are obtained for both plain and 8H satin composites. The experimental results coincide roughly with the predicted curves. A dependency of G_{45} of plain weave on the ply number is found.
- 6) Nonlinear shear constitutive relations in the fill threads and pure matrix regions are examined. The shear deformation of the fill threads is focused on because of a local off-axis angle peculiar to the fabrics. The results are further combined with the nonlinear deformation in the warp regions due to transverse crackings.
- 7) Numerical results of the present theory including the three common types of material nonlinearity for a glass/polyimide 8H satin composite are well correlated with the experimental stress-strain curve.
- 8) A fractional constitutive relation with a quadratic denominator is derived based on the theory of nonlinear elasticity for describing the longitudinal hardening behavior of UD carbon composites because of a requirement for carbon fabric composites.

- 9) A potential of such a fractional relation is demonstrated in an example of a theoretical description of nonlinear stress-strain property of carbon composites with a reinforcement of 8H satin fabrics under the L.W.C condition.
- 10) A geometrical nonlinear description is successfully taken into account for analyzing a behavior of a plain weave composite cured with l-ply prepreg.
- 11) An iterative treatment of the warping induced by the local coupling is included in the one-dimensional analysis.
- 12) The early hardening nonlinearity of thin plain composites is resulting from the allowance of the local warping. The later nonlinear behavior is mainly brought by the longitudinal property of carbon composites.
- 13) The local coupling effect plays the most crucial role in the theory of fabric composites, while the local off-axis angle is trivial for the macroscopic behavior of such composites.

Acknowledgment

The authors wish to express their sincere gratitude to people who make a great assistance in experimentations.

References

- 1) V. Wigotsky, "First Design Details of the All-Composites Lear Fan," Astronautics And Aeronautics, 21 (5) (1983) pp.30-32.
- 2) T. Ishikawa, "Anti-Symmetric Elastic Properties of Composite Plates of Satin Weave Cloth," Fibre Science And Technology, 15 (1981) pp.127-145.
- 3) T. Ishikawa and T. W. Chou, "One-Dimensional Micromechanical Analysis of Woven Fabric Composites," AIAA Journal, 21 (12) (1982) pp.1714-1721.
- 4) T. Ishikawa and T. W. Chou, "Stiffness and Strength Behavior of Woven Fabric Composites," Journal of Materials Science, 17 (1982) pp.3211-3220.
- 5) T. Ishikawa and T. W. Chou, "Nonlinear Behavior of Woven Fabric Composites," Journal Of Composite Materials, 17 (5) (1983) pp.399-413.
- 6) Robert M. Jones, Mechanics of Composite Materials, McGraw-Hill Inc., New York, 1975.
- 7) C. Zweben and J. C. Norman, "Kevlar 49/Thornel 300 Hybrid Fabric Composites for Aerospace Applications," SAMPE Quarterly (1976), pp.1-10.
- 8) N. J. Pagano and J. C. Halpin, "Influence of End Constraint in the Testing of Anisotropic Bodies," Journal Of Composite Materials, 2 (1) (1968), pp.18-31.
- 9) T. Ishikawa, M. Matsushima and Y. Hayashi, "Hardening Nonlinear Behavior in Longitudinal Tension of Unidirectional Carbon Composites," to appear in Journal Of Materials Science.
- 10) Stephen W. Tsai, "Strength Characteristics of Composite Materials," NASA Contractor Report CR-224 (1965).
- 11) H. T. Hahn and S. W. Tsai, "Nonlinear Elastic Behavior of Unidirectional Composite Laminae," Journal Of Composite Materials, 7 (1) (1973), pp.102-118.
- 12) G. J. Curtis, J. M. Milne and W. N. Reynolds, "Non-Hookean Behaviour of Strong Carbon Fibers," Nature, 220 (12) (1968) pp.1024-1025.
- 13) W. H. M. van Dreumel and J. L. M. Kamp, "Non Hookean Behaviour in the Fibre Direction of Carbon-Fibre Composites and the Influence of Fibre Waviness on the Tensile Properties," Journal Of Composite Materials, 11 (4) (1977) pp.461-469.
- 14) T. Ishikawa and T. W. Chou, "In-Plane Thermal Expansion and Thermal Bending Coefficients of Fabric Composites," Journal Of Composite Materials, 17 (2) (1983) pp.92-104.
- 15) S. Kibe et al., "Vibration Tests of Tensile Membrane Structure," s.f.pub.

